

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-LXV. 1-(3',5'-Dinitro-2'-hydroxyphenylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic Acid Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II)

BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA* and A. S. P. MISHRA

Department of Chemistry, G. M. Autonomous College, Sambalpur-768 004

Manuscript received 6 June 1995, accepted 20 November 1995

In our attempt of synthesising polydentate azo dye ligands and polymetallic complexes¹, the present work reports the preparation of a new ON-NO donor bis-bidentate azo dye 1-(3',5'-dinitro-2'-hydroxyphenylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid and its six dinuclear complexes.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have the composition $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$ and $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$, where $M(II) = Co, Ni, Cu$; $M'(II) = Zn, Cd, Hg$. The complexes are amorphous in nature having high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in dimethyl formamide in which they were found to be non-electrolyte ($\Lambda_M = 4.5-6.2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

In the ir spectra of the ligand, the band at 3260 cm^{-1} can be attributed to O-H...N intramolecular hydrogen bonding and its absence in the metal complexes indicates deprotonation of phenolic-OH groups thereby showing its coordination to the metal ions. The sharp bands observed at 1630 and 1510 cm^{-1} in the ligand can be suggested for $\nu_{N=N^2}$ and ν_{C-O^3} vibrations. The bathochromic shift of these bands to *ca* 1610 and 1440 cm^{-1} respectively, indicates the bonding of ligand to the metal ions through both the azo nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes is indicated⁴ by the appearance of broad bands at $3400-3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by sharp peaks at *ca* 840 cm^{-1} assignable to OH stretching and wagging vibrations respectively.

The magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes indicate⁵ the presence of three, two and one unpaired electrons respectively.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex show four bands at 9025 , 18175 , 21295 and 31350 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and CT bands respectively. These transitions suggest an octahedral symmetry around the metal ion⁶. The Ni^{II} complex also displays four bands at 11255 , 18110 , 26950 and 32475 cm^{-1} attributed to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions and CT band respectively. This is in accordance with the earlier reported values for the octahedral Ni^{II} complexes⁷. The Cu^{II} complex reveals one broad asymmetric ligand field band at $13450-15260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in a distorted octahedral geometry⁸.

The 1H nmr spectrum of the ligand displays complex

pattern at δ $6.3-7.7$ due to seven phenyl protons. The phenolic and sulphonic acid protons remain out of the scale. The esr spectrum of the complex $[Cu_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$ was recorded at *X*-band at room temperature. The g_{av} value for the complex is calculated to be 2.1531 by applying Kneubuhl's technique⁹. This type of spectrum may arise due to either dynamic or pseudorotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion of regular octahedral geometry of the complex¹⁰.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are suggested to be four-coordinated with a tetrahedral stereochemistry around the metal ions based on analytical and ir spectral data.

Hence it is concluded that the azo dye behaves as a bis-bidentate chelating ligand capable of coordinating to two metal ions through its azo nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms favouring the formation of dimetallic complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGAND AND THE COMPLEXES

Compd.*/ Colour	Analysis % : (Found/Calcd.)			
	M	C	H	N
LH ₂		43.90	2.20	12.60
Yellow	—	(44.25)	2.32	(12.90)
$[Co_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	15.90	26.20	2.90	7.50
Yellowish green	(16.16)	26.36	3.04	(7.68)
$[Ni_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	16.10	26.20	3.00	7.50
Yellow	(16.11)	26.37	3.04	(7.69)
$[Cu_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	17.10	25.80	2.90	7.50
Green	(17.21)	26.03	3.00	(7.59)
$[Zn_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	19.40	28.50	2.00	8.20
Yellow	(19.52)	28.68	2.11	(8.36)
$[Cd_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	29.30	25.10	1.70	7.20
Yellowish white	(29.42)	25.15	1.85	(7.33)
$[Hg_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	42.50	20.20	1.50	5.80
Grey	(42.66)	20.43	1.50	(5.96)

*LH₂ = 1-(3',5'-dinitro-2'-hydroxyphenylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid.

Experimental

The azo dye was prepared by the usual method. The complexes were prepared by adding an ethanolic solution of the metal(II) chlorides to the ligand solution in dioxan in 2 : 1 ratio and the reaction mixture was warmed for ~1 h over a heating mantle. On cooling concentrated ammonia

NOTE

was added dropwise with stirring and the resulting metal chelates were washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

References

1. B. B. MAHAPATRA, N. P. A. KUMAR and P. K. BHOI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 800; B. B. MAHAPATRA and S. K. KAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 542; B. B. MAHAPATRA and P. K. BHOI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 14.
2. R. B. KING, *Inorg Chem.*, 1965, **5**, 300; R. G. AGARWAL and G. K. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **55**, 681.
3. Y. R. SHARMA, "Elementary Organic Absorption Spectroscopy", S. Chand, New Delhi, 1980.
4. I. GAMO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1961, **34**, 760; K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
5. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINSON, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1960.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier Amsterdam, 1968.
7. L. SACCONI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1968, **61**, 943.
8. L. SACCONI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1968, **4**, 212.
9. F. K. KNEUBUHL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, **33**, 1074
10. B. J. HATHWAY and D. J. E. BILLING, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.